

COLLEMBOLA FROM THE WEST COAST OF ANTARCTIC PENINSULA REGION IN 28th UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC EXPEDITION (2023–2024) SAMPLES

O.V. Protsenko^{1,2}, *P.A. Kovalenko*^{1,3}, *Yu.V. Protsenko*², *A.Yu. Puhovkin*^{1,4,5}, *I.Yu. Parnikoza*^{1,6},
*I.A. Kozeretska*¹

¹ State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; Protsenko.Olexandra@gmail.com;

² Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine;

³ State Institution “Institute for Evolutionary Ecology”, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine;

⁴ Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;

⁵ Institute for Problems of Cryobiology and Cryomedicine, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine;

⁶ Institute of Molecular Biology of Ukraine, National Academy of Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

The study of Collembola (springtails) in the Antarctic region began in the late XIX century, and their diversity and distribution are now relatively well described. However, ecosystem changes driven by both global warming and direct human impact are altering historically established species assemblages. Therefore, it is crucial to study the dynamics of Collembola communities in Maritime Antarctica.

Species diversity data for the current study were collected from December 2023 to March 2024. A total of 142 samples were obtained from 35 localities across different plant substrates (e.g., *Larus dominicanus* and *Stercorarius maccormicki* nest material, *Sanionia georgicouncinata*, *Warnstorfia fontinaliopsis*, *Polytrichum strictum*, *Bryum pseudotriquetrum*, *Andreaea* sp., *Syntrichia* sp., *Cratoneuroopsis relaxa*, *Ceratodon purpureus*, *Deschampsia antarctica*, *Prasiola crispa*, etc.). Sampling was conducted in several regions along the western coast of the Antarctic Peninsula, including the South Shetland Islands, Chavez Island, Wilhelm Archipelago, Kyiv Peninsula, Berthelot Islands, Darboux Island, Lahille Island, Pitt Islands, and Adelaide-Biscoe Archipelago. Collembolan samples were preserved in 96% ethanol, frozen, and transported to Ukraine for further analysis.

Three Collembola species were identified: *Cryptopygus antarcticus*, *Frisea grisea*, and *Folsomotoma octooculata*. All three species were documented in 21 localities, including Nelson I. (South Shetland Islands), Booth I., Hovgaard I., Petermann I., Eight I., Fanfare I., Galindez I., Uruguay I., Skua I., Corner I., Yalour Is., an un-named island of the Barchans, Locator Is. (Roca Islands) (Wilhelm Archipelago), Girard Bay (Girard Bay Oasis), Cape Perez, Cape Rasmussen, Mount Waugh (Kyiv Peninsula), Berthelot Islands, Darboux I., the largest un-named island of the Lipmann Islands, and Hook Is. (Adelaide-Biscoe Archipelago).

Two species (*C. antarcticus* and *F. grisea*) were found on six islands: Central Pig I., Grotto I., Irizar I. (Wilhelm Archipelago), Krivus I. (Pitt Islands), Adelaide I., and Avian I. (Adelaide-Biscoe Archipelago).

Only *C. antarcticus* was recorded in seven localities: Anchorage Is., Leonie Is. (Adelaide-Biscoe Archipelago), two un-named islands of the Pitt Islands, Cape Tuxen (Kyiv Peninsula), an un-named of the Cruls Islands (Wilhelm Archipelago), and Chavez Is.

On Lahille Island, only *F. octooculata* was found.

Based on literature data analysis, springtails are reported for the first time from 25 localities: Chavez I., Booth I., Central Pig I., an un-named island of the Barchans, Corner I., Cruls Islands, Eight I., Grotto I., Skua I., Hovgaard I., Locator Island (Roca Islands) (Wilhelm Archipelago), Girard Bay,

Cape Perez, Cape Rasmussen, Cape Tuxen, Mount Waugh (Kyiv Peninsula), Darboux Is., the largest un-named island of the Lipmann Islands, Lahille I., Krivus I. and two un-named islands of the Pitt Islands, Avian Is., Hook Is., and Leonie Is. (Adelaide-Biscoe Archipelago).

Additionally, species lists were expanded for Adelaide I., *F. grisea* was newly recorded, increasing the total species count to two.